

Research Article

Genotype-Environment Interaction and Stability for Yield of Inbred and Hybrid Rainfed Lowland Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) Varieties in Bangladesh

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Abstract: Forty-eight rice genotypes of inbred and hybrid rice varieties developed or registered by different organizations were evaluated for their stability for grain yield through regression coefficient and deviation from regression analysis. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications at seven locations of Bangladesh. Highly significant mean sum of squares due to genotype and environment and pooled deviation indicated sufficient variability among the genotypes and environments for yield and revealed the importance of a non-linear component accounting for the total genotype-environment interaction. Khulna (E3) was found as most favorable location because of showing highest environmental mean yield and environmental index. The stability parameters for grain yield revealed wider adaptability of the genotypes V5 (BRRI dhan30), V13 (BRRI dhan49), V29 (Binadhan-17), V33 (Mukti-1), V34 (Agro dhan-12), V35 (Bayer hybrid dhan-4) and V41 (BADC hybrid dhan-6). The genotypes V32 (BRRI hybrid dhan6), V1 (BR10), V40 (BADC hybrid dhan-2), V15 (BRRI dhan52), V7 (BRRI dhan32), V21 (BRRI dhan72), V20 (BRRI dhan71), V30 (Binadhan-7), V6 (BRRI dhan31), V31 (BRRI hybrid dhan4), V26 (Binadhan-11), V19 (BRRI dhan66), V48 (Bindhan-4), V24 (BU dhan-1), V22 (BRRI dhan73), V38 (Hera-16), V44 (BRRI dhan44), V36 (Bayer hybrid dhan-6), V2 (BR22), V46 (BR11) and V43 (BRRI dhan75) showed insignificant regression coefficient (b_i) values and higher mean yield than the grand mean and positive phenotypic index (P_i) indicating them to be suitable for poor environment.

Keywords: *Rice, Stability parameter, Phenotypic index, Regression coefficient, Deviation from regression*

INTRODUCTION

Rice is the staple food in Bangladesh. Globally it is grown extensively in tropical and sub-tropical region under diverse climatic and edaphic condition of the world. Rice grows in all the three crop growing seasons of the year and occupies about 77% of the total cropped area. Bangladesh agriculture is involved with the food production for 163.65 million people from merely 8.75 million hectares of agricultural land (Salam *et al.*, 2014). More food will be required in future because of increasing population. Population of Bangladesh will reach 215.4 million in 2050, when 44.6 MT of clean rice will be needed. In 2014-15, the country acquired a rice surplus of about 2.0 MT. However, maintaining the current surplus of rice in coming decades is a great challenge. Authentic estimation of future rice requirement and future resource availability would guide to way forward (Kabir *et al.*, 2015). Development of location specific variety has been considered very important for achieving the future challenge of sustainable food production (Iftekharuddaula *et al.*, 2002).

Yield is a complex quantitative character and is greatly influenced by environmental fluctuations; hence, multi-environment trial may be very effective for the selection of stable genotypes based on yield. Thus, evaluation of genotypes for stability of performance under varying environmental conditions for yield has become an essential part of any breeding programme (Berger *et al.*, 2007). G-E interaction should be investigated so that the breeder can decide to restructure the programme to minimize the interaction effect, or exploit it to produce varieties with specific adaptation to particular environments (Eisemann *et al.*, 1990). A key concept in G x E analysis is genotype stability and by definition, genotypes exhibiting a high degree of G x E interaction are unstable across sites (Berger *et al.*, 2007).

The assessment of stability and wider adaptability of breeding lines against biotic and abiotic stresses is a pre-requisite in any breeding programme. Stability analysis was successfully used to determine stable genotypes, carry out genotype-environment interaction and identify the genotypes for low and high yielding environments. It is the ability to show a minimum interaction with the environment (Eberhart and Russell, 1966). Hence, the stability of genotype is directly related to the effect of G x E (Campbell and Jones, 2005). The adaptability of a variety over diverse environments is usually tested by the degree of its interaction with different environments under which it is tested (Finlay and Wilkinson, 1963).

Bangladesh Rice Research Institute and other organizations even private sectors have developed a good number of inbred and hybrid varieties for irrigated ecosystems but not all of these varieties except BRRI dhan28 and BRRI dhan29 are well adapted across all the agro-ecological zones. Therefore, in the present efforts were made to characterize the stability of the studied genotypes and find out the genotype-environment interactions for yield in the different agro-climatic conditions of Bangladesh.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Forty-eight genotypes consisting BRRI, BINA, BADC and other private companies were evaluated in seven locations of Bangladesh. The seven locations were Dhaka, Rajshahi, Rangpur, Barishal, Chattogram, Khulna and Sylhet. The experiment was conducted in rainfed lowland rice ecosystem in 2018-19. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The unit plot size was 5.4 m × 10 rows and the transplanting was done following 20 cm × 15 cm spacing in all the locations. Thirty five to forty days old seedlings were transplanted with two to three seedlings per hill. Fertilizers were applied @ 100:80:60:100:10 kg per hectare N, P₂O₅, K₂O, Gypsum and ZnSO₄. Nitrogen (N) was applied in three split applications @ 50:40:40 kg per hectare at 10-15 days after transplanting, maximum tillering and before panicle initiation stage. Total amount of P, K, Gypsum and ZnSO₄ were applied at final land preparation. Standard cultural practices were followed in all the locations to raise a good crop.

Grain yield (t/ha) was recorded at maturity by harvesting whole plot and adjusted at 14% moisture content. Combined analysis of variance for stability was done according to Sharma (1998). The phenotypic index (P_i) was determined following Ram *et al.*, (1970). It was the deviation of the i^{th} variety from the overall mean. The other stability parameters i.e. the regression coefficient (b_i), deviation from regression coefficient (S^2_{di}) were estimated after Eberhart and Russell (1966). Significance of differences among b_i value and unity was tested by t-test, and among S^2_{di} and zero by F-test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of combined analysis of variance for grain yield of 48 rice genotypes are shown in Table 1. Highly significant mean sum of squares due to genotypes and environment indicated sufficient variability among the genotypes and environments for yield. Similar results were reported by Biswas *et al.* (1999), Iftakharuddaula *et al.* (2002), Hossain *et al.* (2007) and Khatun

et al. (2010) in rice. Significant e (linear) variance means variation among environments is linear. A linear environmental variance would signify unit changes in environmental index for each unit change in the environmental conditions. Highly significant mean squares due to pooled deviation for yield revealed the importance of a non-linear component accounting for the total genotype-environment interaction.

Table 1. Combined analysis of variance for grain yield of 48 rice varieties of T.Aman 2018-19

Source of variation	df	SS	MS	F	F at 5%	F at 1%	Significance
Genotypes (g)	47	70.59	1.502	2.210	1.4216	1.631	**
Environments (e)	6	98.15	16.358	24.073	2.136	2.89	**
g x e	282	180.93	0.642	0.944	1.239	1.342	ns
e + (g x e)	288	279.09	0.969	1.426	1.228	1.357	**
e (linear)	1	98.15	98.151	144.437	3.884	6.748	**
g x e (linear)	47	17.84	0.380	0.559	1.4216	1.631	ns
Pooled Deviation	240	163.09	0.680	4.283	1.2	1.29	**
Total	335	349.68	1.044				

** Significant at 1% level of probability

Relatively higher value of the linear component as compared to non-linear one suggested the possibility of prediction of performance for yield over the environments. Therefore, linear (b_i) and nonlinear (S^2_{di}) component of G-E interactions were considered while judging the phenotypic stability of a genotype (Finlay and Wilkinson, 1963; Eberhart and Russell, 1966). They further suggested that an ideal variety should have high mean with linear regression coefficient equal to unity and S^2_{di} as small as possible.

Table 2. Location wise mean yield (t/ha), Co-efficient of variation (CV), Heritability in broad sense (h^2) and environmental index of 48 rainfed lowland rice varieties in seven environments

Varieties	Code	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	Mean
BR10	V1	5.30	5.37	4.67	4.47	3.20	5.13	4.43	4.65
BR22	V2	2.17	5.03	5.10	2.60	2.91	5.23	5.60	4.09
BR23	V3	4.00	4.23	3.80	2.60	2.89	4.87	5.63	4.00
BR25	V4	1.63	3.53	5.13	2.67	2.79	3.23	4.37	3.34
BRRI dhan30	V5	3.83	4.63	5.03	3.70	3.12	4.33	5.23	4.27
BRRI dhan31	V6	5.43	4.63	5.23	3.27	3.06	4.53	4.67	4.40
BRRI dhan32	V7	5.73	5.07	5.20	3.47	3.06	4.83	4.60	4.57
BRRI dhan34	V8	3.12	3.13	3.57	3.40	1.37	3.23	4.03	3.12
BRRI dhan37	V9	2.37	5.30	3.67	2.83	2.16	3.03	3.13	3.21
BRRI dhan38	V10	1.90	4.23	3.70	2.97	2.34	3.33	3.43	3.13
BRRI dhan39	V11	4.70	2.00	4.50	2.83	2.55	3.63	4.07	3.47
BRRI dhan46	V12	3.94	4.57	4.63	2.57	3.04	4.23	4.60	3.94

BRRI dhan49	V13	4.10	4.37	5.70	4.07	3.03	4.83	5.13	4.46
BRRI dhan51	V14	2.23	5.77	4.00	2.70	2.77	3.53	4.00	3.57
BRRI dhan52	V15	4.40	5.57	5.10	3.30	3.14	5.03	5.63	4.60
BRRI dhan56	V16	3.67	1.83	4.77	4.17	3.27	3.53	3.93	3.60
BRRI dhan57	V17	3.03	2.60	4.10	4.27	3.05	3.03	3.57	3.38
BRRI dhan62	V18	4.33	3.00	4.00	4.03	2.74	3.00	4.03	3.59
BRRI dhan66	V19	5.83	3.40	4.00	5.07	3.58	3.83	4.33	4.29
BRRI dhan71	V20	4.37	3.90	4.33	5.43	3.54	4.50	5.33	4.49
BRRI dhan72	V21	2.97	5.13	5.50	5.07	3.35	4.63	5.20	4.55
BRRI dhan73	V22	5.13	3.60	5.37	5.10	3.13	3.53	3.57	4.20
Binasail	V23	5.10	2.90	4.10	3.70	2.89	3.00	3.90	3.66
BU dhan-1	V24	5.13	4.30	4.67	5.10	2.94	3.43	4.40	4.28
BU dhan-2	V25	2.80	3.57	4.00	3.37	3.54	3.00	4.50	3.54
Binadhan-11	V26	3.97	3.90	4.17	5.50	3.14	3.93	5.87	4.35
Binadhan-12	V27	1.93	4.43	4.17	3.43	2.92	4.23	4.67	3.68
Binadhan-16	V28	4.97	3.27	4.17	5.50	2.47	3.30	3.00	3.81
Binadhan-17	V29	3.50	4.43	6.03	4.77	3.33	4.30	4.60	4.42
Binadhan-7	V30	5.53	4.40	4.10	4.67	2.86	4.03	5.67	4.47
BRRI hybrid dhan4	V31	4.13	4.38	6.17	4.93	3.12	4.50	3.40	4.38
BRRI hybrid dhan6	V32	6.43	5.07	6.43	5.47	3.38	4.67	4.97	5.20
Mukti-1(HB-12)	V33	4.40	3.93	4.97	4.53	2.95	3.73	5.37	4.27
Agro dhan-12	V34	4.27	4.63	4.67	4.30	3.38	3.83	4.47	4.22
Bayer hybrid dhan-4	V35	3.67	5.00	5.47	3.90	3.03	4.27	5.37	4.39
Bayer hybrid dhan-6	V36	4.00	4.93	5.43	3.20	3.48	2.43	5.30	4.11
Hera-10	V37	4.70	4.03	5.23	3.63	2.98	2.07	5.27	3.99
Hera-16	V38	5.40	4.14	4.97	3.23	2.75	3.90	4.57	4.14
Suborna-8	V39	3.93	3.60	4.03	3.07	2.98	3.53	4.87	3.72
BADC hybrid dhan-2	V40	3.83	4.50	6.13	4.30	4.81	4.43	4.37	4.63
BADC hybrid dhan-6	V41	4.43	4.70	5.63	4.60	3.60	4.60	4.23	4.54
BADC hybrid dhan-4	V42	4.53	2.40	4.67	3.43	3.07	3.33	3.27	3.53
BRRI dhan75	V43	4.97	3.80	5.70	3.80	2.26	3.70	4.13	4.05
BRRI dhan44	V44	1.43	5.13	5.53	3.77	2.85	5.20	4.93	4.12
BRRI dhan33	V45	2.93	5.43	4.03	3.00	2.75	4.37	4.07	3.80
BR11	V46	1.57	4.87	6.13	3.07	2.68	4.73	5.47	4.07
Binadhan-15	V47	1.67	5.23	4.67	2.83	3.27	4.10	3.97	3.68
Binadhan-4	V48	1.33	4.93	6.17	4.40	3.57	4.40	5.23	4.29
Env. Mean		3.85	4.23	4.84	3.88	3.02	3.96	4.55	4.05
Env. Index		-0.20	0.18	0.80	-0.17	-1.02	-0.09	0.51	0.00
CV%		21.31	8.44	7.70	4.42	6.4	3.95	10.1	10.4
LSD at 5%		1.29	0.57	0.59	0.27	0.31	0.25	0.74	0.84
Heritability		0.87	0.95	0.92	0.99	0.95	0.99	0.87	0.59

(Remarks, E1=Dhaka; E2=Chattogram; E3=Khulna; E4=Rajshahi; E5=Rangpur; E6=Sylhet; E7=Barishal)

In the present study, it was observed that the highest yield was obtained in E3 (4.84 t/ha) followed by E7 (4.55 t/ha) and E2 (4.23 t/ha). Positive environmental index in the location E2 (0.18), E3 (0.80) and E7 (0.51) indicated higher yield performance potential of the three

locations. E3 was the most favorable location followed by E2 and E7 suggested almost all the genotypes had the potential to exploit these three locations. The quality of the mean data could be considered reliable due to considerable CV (10.4%) and moderate broad sense heritability (0.59) in pooled analysis (Table 2).

Table 3. Genotype-wise mean yield (t/ha) and stability parameters for 48 rice genotypes evaluated under rainfed lowland condition in seven environments

Varieties	Code	Mean	P _i	b _i	Sig.	S ² _{di}	Sig.	Comments
BRRI hybrid dhan-6	V32	5.20	1.15	1.20	ns	0.60	**	High yield High sensitivity
BR10	V1	4.65	0.61	0.67	ns	0.33	**	High yield High sensitivity
BADC hybrid dhan-2	V40	4.63	0.58	0.53	ns	0.36	**	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan52	V15	4.60	0.55	1.38	ns	0.33	**	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan32	V7	4.57	0.52	1.02	ns	0.53	**	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan72	V21	4.55	0.50	1.29	ns	0.34	**	High yield High sensitivity
BADC hybrid dhan-6	V41	4.54	0.50	0.84	ns	0.00	ns	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan71	V20	4.49	0.44	0.50	ns	0.32	*	High yield High sensitivity
Binadhan-7	V30	4.47	0.42	0.85	ns	0.65	**	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan49	V13	4.46	0.41	1.41	ns	-0.08	ns	High yield High sensitivity
Binadhan-17	V29	4.42	0.38	1.29	ns	0.13	ns	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan31	V6	4.40	0.36	1.07	ns	0.37	**	High yield High sensitivity
Bayer hybrid dhan-4	V35	4.39	0.34	1.51	ns	-0.07	ns	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI hybrid dhan-4	V31	4.38	0.33	1.06	ns	0.61	**	High yield High sensitivity
Binadhan-11	V26	4.35	0.31	0.82	ns	0.69	**	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan66	V19	4.29	0.24	-0.02	ns	0.76	**	High yield Poor sensitivity
Binadhan-4	V48	4.29	0.24	1.65	ns	1.55	**	High yield High sensitivity
BU dhan-1	V24	4.28	0.23	0.74	ns	0.43	**	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan30	V5	4.27	0.22	1.23	ns	-0.08	ns	High yield High sensitivity
Mukti-1(HB-12)	V33	4.27	0.22	1.16	ns	0.07	ns	High yield High sensitivity
Agro dhan-12	V34	4.22	0.17	0.70	ns	-0.10	ns	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan73	V22	4.20	0.16	0.65	ns	0.75	**	High yield High sensitivity
Hera-16	V38	4.14	0.09	1.09	ns	0.41	**	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan44	V44	4.12	0.07	1.72	ns	1.39	**	High yield High sensitivity
Bayer hybrid dhan-6	V36	4.11	0.06	1.35	ns	0.67	**	High yield High sensitivity
BR22	V2	4.09	0.04	1.70	ns	1.22	**	High yield High sensitivity
BR11	V46	4.07	0.03	2.21	*	1.14	**	High yield High sensitivity
BRRI dhan75	V43	4.05	0.00	1.48	ns	0.34	**	High yield High sensitivity
BR23	V3	4.00	-0.04	0.98	ns	0.79	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
Hera-10	V37	3.99	-0.06	1.35	ns	0.80	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
BRRI dhan46	V12	3.94	-0.11	1.04	ns	0.22	*	Low yield High Sensitivity
Binadhan-16	V28	3.81	-0.24	0.33	ns	1.26	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
BRRI dhan33	V45	3.80	-0.25	0.95	ns	0.59	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
Suborna-8	V39	3.72	-0.33	0.80	ns	0.07	ns	Low yield High Sensitivity
Binadhan-12	V27	3.68	-0.36	1.04	ns	0.55	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
Binadhan-15	V47	3.68	-0.37	1.05	ns	1.11	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
Binasail	V23	3.66	-0.39	0.44	ns	0.55	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
BRRI dhan56	V16	3.60	-0.45	0.50	ns	0.75	**	Low yield High Sensitivity

BRRRI dhan62	V18	3.59	-0.46	0.56	ns	0.22	*	Low yield High Sensitivity
BRRRI dhan51	V14	3.57	-0.48	1.07	ns	1.05	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
BU dhan-2	V25	3.54	-0.51	0.53	ns	0.13	ns	Low yield High Sensitivity
BADC hybrid dhan-4	V42	3.53	-0.52	0.43	ns	0.55	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
BRRRI dhan39	V11	3.47	-0.58	0.81	ns	0.85	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
BRRRI dhan57	V17	3.38	-0.67	0.40	ns	0.24	*	Low yield High Sensitivity
BR25	V4	3.34	-0.71	1.47	ns	0.55	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
BRRRI dhan37	V9	3.21	-0.83	0.99	ns	0.76	**	Low yield High Sensitivity
BRRRI dhan38	V10	3.13	-0.92	0.91	ns	0.27	*	Low yield High Sensitivity
BRRRI dhan34	V8	3.12	-0.92	1.25	ns	0.04	ns	Low yield High Sensitivity

** and * significant at 1% and 5% level of probability respectively

The average yield of the genotypes under different environments and the mean yield over all environments along with P_i , b_i , S^2_{di} estimates are presented in Table 3. Finlay & Wilkinson (1963) reported that the regression coefficient (b_i) is a measure of stability in crop plants. Eberhart & Russell (1966) proposed that both regression coefficient (b_i) and mean square deviation from regression coefficient (S^2_{di}) may be taken into consideration in identifying stable genotypes. So, genotypes V1 (BR10), V10 (BRRRI dhan38), V11 (BRRRI dhan39), V16 (BRRRI dhan56), V17 (BRRRI dhan57), V18 (BRRRI dhan62), V19 (BRRRI dhan66), V20 (BRRRI dhan71), V22 (BRRRI dhan73), V23 (Binasail), V24 (BU dhan-1), V25 (Bu dhan-2), V26 (Binadhan-11), V28 (Binadhan-16), V30 (Binadhan-7), V34 (Agro dhan-12), V39 (Suborna-8), V40 (BADC hybrid dhan-2), V41 (BADC hybrid dhan-6) and V42 (BADC hybrid dhan-4) with b_i value <1.0 has above average stability and is specially adapted to low performing environments or sensitivity to environment i.e. little change in yield despite large changes in environment.

Genotypes V2 (BR22), V4 (BR25), V5 (BRRRI dhan30), V8 (BRRRI dhan34), V13 (BRRRI dhan49), V15 (BRRRI dhan52), V21 (BRRRI dhan72), V29 (Binadhan-17), V32 (BRRRI hybrid dhan6), V33 (Mukti-1), V35 (Bayer hybrid dhan-4), V36 (Bayer hybrid dhan-6), V37 (Hera-10), V43 (BRRRI dhan75), V44 (BRRRI dhan44), V46 (BR11) and V48 (Binadhan-4) with b_i value >1.0 has below average stability and is specially adapted to high performing environments and they are highly sensitive to environmental changes as the rate of change in genotype for every unit change in environment are high. On the other words, small changes in environment produce large changes in yield. Thus under most favorable environment, such varieties may yield the highest.

Genotypes V3 (BR23), V6 (BRRRI dhan31), V7 (BRRRI dhan32), V9 (BRRRI dhan37), V12 (BRRRI dhan46), V14 (BRRRI dhan51), V27 (Binadhan-12), V31 (BRRRI hybrid dhan4), V38 (Hera-16), V45 (BRRRI dhan33) and V47 (Binadhan-15) with b_i value close to 1.0 has average stability and

is well or poorly adapted to all environments depending on having a high or low mean performance (Finlay & Wilkinson, 1963). Genotypes V32 (BRRI hybrid dhan6), V1 (BR10), V40 (BADC hybrid dhan-2), V15 (BRRI dhan52), V7 (BRRI dhan32), V21 (BRRI dhan72), V41 (BADC hybrid dhan-6), V20 (BRRI dhan71), V30 (Binadhan-7), V13 (BRRI dhan49), V29 (Binadhan-17) and V6 (BRRI dhan31) have mean yield higher than 4.40 t/ha. V32 (BRRI hybrid dhan6) showed comparatively high positive phenotypic index (1.15) followed by BR10 (0.61) suggesting, these two genotypes to be high performing among all the genotypes and may be widely adapted.

V5 (BRRI dhan30), V13 (BRRI dhan49), V29 (Binadhan-17), V33 (Mukti-1), V34 (Agro dhan-12), V35 (Bayer hybrid dhan-4) and V41 (BADC hybrid dhna-6) had a positive P_i value, insignificant regression coefficient (b_i) values near to unity ($b=1$) with insignificant S^2_{di} (deviation from regression) and mean yield higher than the grand mean indicating their stability in yield with the changes of environments and possessed better adaptability over wider range of environments. Abassi *et al.* (1991); Aditya *et al.* (2010) and Khatun *et al.* (2010) reported similar adaptability in rice. Finlay and Wilkinson (1963) suggested that cultivar with regression coefficient (b_i) around 1.0 would be stable. However, this genotype may be used directly as a variety or it may be used in the crossing program too.

V3 (BR23), V37 (Hera-10), V12 (BRRI dhan46), V28 (Binadhan-16), V45 (BRRI dhan33), V39 (Suborna-8), V27 (Binadhan-12), V47 (Binadhan-15), V23 (Binasail), V16 (BRRI dhan56), V18 (BRRI dhan62), V14 (BRRI dhan51), V25 (BU dhan-2), V42 (BADC hybrid dhan-4), V11 (BRRI dhan39), V17 (BRRI dhan57), V4 (BR25), V9 (BRRI dhan37), V10 (BRRI dhan38) and V8 (BRRI dhan34) were unacceptable due to their negative P_i values. None of the genotypes except V46 (BR11) showed combined b_i and S^2_{di} sensitivity, suggesting that either linear or non-linear component alone was responsible for genotype-environment interaction. The results were supported by the findings of Ray *et al.* (1991) and Iftekharudduala *et al.* (2002). Considering b_i value close to unity with insignificant deviation from regression, V8 (BRRI dhan34), V25 (BU dhan-2) and V39 (Suborna-8) may also be assumed as stable one but it was not accepted because the mean yield was below the grand mean having negative phenotypic index. Ray *et al.* (1998) and Biswas *et al.* (1999) also found such type of unacceptable rice genotype with stable yield.

V32 (BRRI hybrid dhan6), V1 (BR10), V40 (BADC hybrid dhan-2), V15 (BRRI dhan52), V7 (BRRI dhan32), V21 (BRRI dhan72), V20 (BRRI dhan71), V30 (Binadhan-7), V6 (BRRI

dhan31), V31 (BRRI hybrid dhan4), V26 (Binadhan-11), V19 (BRRI dhan66), V48 (Bindhan-4), V24 (BU dhan-1), V22 (BRRI dhan73), V38 (Hera-16), V44 (BRRI dhan44), V36 (Bayer hybrid dhan-6), V2 (BR22), V46 (BR11) and V43 (BRRI dhan75) V32 (BRRI hybrid dhan6), V1 (BR10), V40 (BADC hybrid dhan-2), V15 (BRRI dhan52), V7 (BRRI dhan32), V21 (BRRI dhan72), V20 (BRRI dhan71), V30 (Binadhan-7), V6 (BRRI dhan31), V31 (BRRI hybrid dhan4), V26 (Binadhan-11), V19 (BRRI dhan66), V48 (Bindhan-4), V24 (BU dhan-1), V22 (BRRI dhan73), V38 (Hera-16), V44 (BRRI dhan44), V36 (Bayer hybrid dhan-6), V2 (BR22), V46 (BR11) and V43 (BRRI dhan75) showed significant deviation from regression indicating their instability but their insignificant regression coefficient (b_i) values along with higher mean yield than the grand mean and positive phenotypic index (P_i) suggests them to be suitable for poor environment.

Fig.1: Adaptive specificities of 48 genotypes of rainfed lowland rice.

The adaptive specificities of forty eight V genotypes for grain yield have been shown in Fig.1, where the genotypes have been categorized into four classes which are i) High yield, high sensitivity ii) Low yield, high sensitivity iii) Low yield, poor sensitivity iv) High yield, poor sensitivity. It was found that none of the genotypes were found in the last two categories.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare. ©

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